

TABLE 1—PMR, UV AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF PALLADIUM AND COBALTC COMPLEXES

Complex	Elemental analysis								PMR signals in τ with respect to TMS	Electronic absorption bands in kK (ϵ)	
	Calculated				Found					Methanol	Chloroform
	C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M			
HINBA	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.4, 2.18-2.62, 7.55	39.2	39.2
HINDBM	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.5, 1.88-2.64, —	39.0	39.4
Pd(INBA) ₂	49.3	3.3	5.7	21.8	48.2	3.8	5.9	21.0	—, 2.34-2.70, 7.55	40.3(4999), 25.6(4700)	40.3(1693), 24.7(3725)
Co(INBA) ₂	57.2	3.8	6.6	9.34	56.9	3.9	6.6	9.36	—, 2.00-2.60, 7.50	40.7(15630), 35.7(13110), 27.8(5771)	27.8(18870)
Pd(INDBM) ₂	59.0	3.3	4.6	17.4	60.0	3.5	4.9	17.4	—, 2.20-2.80, —	39.4(6542), 25.0(3763)	39.4(24770), 24.3(25450)
Co(INDBM) ₂	66.2	3.7	5.1	7.2	65.8	3.6	4.9	7.4	—, 1.80-2.80, —	—	27.8(41190)

stretching. The bands at 1595 and 1575 cm^{-1} in the complexes are attributed to perturbed C=O and or C=N stretching. The bands at 1575 cm^{-1} may also be assigned to C=C stretching frequency. The ν_{NO} observed in the region 1240–1225 cm^{-1} indicates that the coordination of the metal has taken through nitrogen of the oxime group. The bands at 612 and 600 cm^{-1} observed in Pd(INDBM)₂ and Co(INDBM)₂ complexes may be assigned to M-N vibration mode.

The electronic spectrum of HINBA and HINDBM in methanol and chloroform solution show one absorption band at 39.0–39.4 kK which may be assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in the ligand. The intensity of this band increases in Pd(INBA)₂ (40.3 kK, $\epsilon=4999$ in CH₃OH; 40.3 kK, $\epsilon=1693$ in CHCl₃), and Pd(INDBM)₂ (39.4 kK, $\epsilon=6542$ in CH₃OH; 39.4 kK, $\epsilon=24770$ in CHCl₃) complexes. Both Pd(INBA)₂ and Pd(INDBM)₂ in methanol show one more absorption band at 25.6 kK and 25.0 kK respectively which may be assigned to charge transfer transitions. In chloroform these band shift to 24.7 kK and 24.3 kK respectively. Co(INBA)₂ in methanol show three absorption bands. The bands at 40.7 kK ($\epsilon=15630$) and 35.7 kK ($\epsilon=13110$) may be attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition whereas the charge transfer transition appears at 27.8 kK ($\epsilon=571$). Co(INBA)₂ and Co(INDBM)₂ in chloroform show charge transfer bands at 27.8 kK.

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References

1. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Analyst*, 1979, 140, 160.
2. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1979, 295, 412.
3. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1979, 298, 158.
4. BEILSTEIN, *Handbuch Der organische Chemie*, Band VII, 864, 1409.

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Some Trivalent Rare Earths with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2-Iminopyridine**

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IN continuation to our earlier studies on Schiff-base ligands and their metal complexes^{1,2}, we report in the present communication our potentiometric studies of the proton-ligand stability constants of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2-iminopyridine and its formation of 1:1 complexes with Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and Gd(III).

All chemicals and reagents used in the study were either of A.R. grade or purified before use.

The Schiff-base ligand was prepared by an analogous method as described in our earlier paper². The purity of the ligand was checked by elemental analysis and melting point determination.

Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution³ and double distilled water were used. Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates and were estimated by EDTA method⁴. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1M HClO₄ to avoid metal hydrolysis.

A digital pH-meter of Electronics Corporation of India, model No. pH-5651 (accuracy ± 0.01 unit) with combined glass electrode assembly was used for the present study. All computation works were done in programmable calculator (EC 62 p) of Electronics Corporation of India.

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Bjerrum - Calvin^{6,6} pH titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti⁷ was followed to determine the formation constant values. Following sets of titrations were performed at a constant ionic strength 0.1M NaClO₄ in 50% (v/v) acetone-water medium at 30±1°.

- i) 10 ml 0.1M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1M NaClO₄ + 10 ml water + 25 ml acetone.
- ii) Solution mixture (i) + 4×10⁻³M ligand.
- iii) 5 ml 0.1M HClO₄ + 5 ml 1M NaClO₄ + 5 ml 0.01M metal solution + 4×10⁻³M ligand + 25 ml acetone + 10 ml water.

The total volume in each case was kept constant (50 ml) initially and the ratio of metal salt to reagent was maintained at nearly 1:4 in all titrations in order to satisfy the maximum coordination possibility of the metal ions.

From the titration curves using solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_H values at various "B" values (pH-meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve between "B" and corresponding \bar{n}_H was plotted [Fig. 1A]. The

Fig. 1. A-Plot of \bar{n}_H against pH-meter reading. B-Plot of e^2/r against $\log K_1$ values.

values for the "practical" proton-ligand stability constants $\log {}^P K_1^H$ and $\log {}^P K_2^H$ were evaluated by using

(i) Bjerrum's half-integral method and (ii) pointwise calculation method⁸. The values agree closely. In the light of our discussion in the earlier paper², $\log {}^P K_1^H$ value (7.8) has been assigned to the proton dissociation of the phenolic OH and the $\log {}^P K_2^H$ value (6.4) to the proton-affinity value of the pyridine nitrogen of the Schiff base ligand under study.

From the titration curves using solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} (metal-ligand formation, number) and PL (free ligand concentration) were calculated by using the following relations :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + V') T_0^0 M} \times \frac{1}{\bar{n}_H} \quad \dots (1)$$

(where $T_0^0 M$ denote the total concentration of metal present in the solution and other terms have their usual meanings) and

$$PL = \log \frac{\left[\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H (1/\text{anti log } B)^n (V^0 + V''') \right]}{[(TcL^0 - \bar{n} TcM^0) V^0]} \quad \dots (2)$$

(where β_n^H is the overall "practical" proton-ligand stability constant). The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the metal ligand formation curves (Fig. 2). The values of metal-ligand stability constant $\log K_1$ were calculated by (i) pointwise calculation and (ii) Bjerrum half-integral method. The values are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - STABILITY CONSTANT OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE-2-IMINOPYRIDINE WITH RARE EARTH METALS AT $\mu = 0.1M$ NaClO₄ IN 50% (v/v) ACETONE-WATER MEDIUM AT (30°±1°)

	H ⁺ $\log {}^P K_1^H$	$\log {}^P K_2^H$	Pr(III)	Nd(III)	Sm(III)	Gd(III)
Bjerrum half \bar{n} method	7.800	6.430	5.100	5.900	4.850	4.80
Pointwise calculation	7.875	6.412	5.100	5.875	4.950	4.875
$\log \beta_n$		14.259	5.100	5.888	4.900	4.838

The maximum value of \bar{n} was near about 0.8 and this indicates 1:1 complexation below the region of metal hydrolysis. The order of stabilities of metal complexes is Gd(III) < Sm(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III).

Rare earths, with their 4f orbitals being well-shielded, usually form ionic compounds and are expected to obey the Born relationship⁹. The possibility of some covalent interaction, however, cannot be completely excluded as reported in the case of acetylaceton complexes of rare-earths¹⁰. In the present study, the $\log K_1$ values of 1:1 metal-ligand complexes have been plotted against e^2/r (Fig. 1 B). Though some amount

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand formation curves.

of ionic character may be suggested to the metal-ligand bonding, the plots, however, do not exhibit any complete linear relationship. Such a difference in the trend of stability constant is not uncommon in the case of lanthanide complexes¹¹⁻¹³ and this may be due to varying degree of stabilization arising out of interaction of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field¹⁴.

The absence of 1:2 chelates in the present case may be due to steric hindrance produced by the attached ligand in the 1:1 chelate to the approach of the second one.

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References

1. R. L. DUTTA and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 83.
2. C. R. BERA, S. CHATTOPADHYAY and G. P. SENGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 416.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Longman Publication, London, 1961, p. 239.
4. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations" Methuen & Co. Ltd. London, 1956, p. 60.
5. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution" P. Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941.

6. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M.B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1011.
9. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolytic Solutions", (Butterworths, London), 1959, 355.
10. T. MOELLER, D.F. MARTIN, L. C. THOMPSON, R. FERRUS, G. R. FEISTEL and W. J. RANDALL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
11. F. H. SPEDDING, J. E. POWEL and E. J. WHEELWRIGHT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 34.
12. J. SCHWARZENBACH and R. GUT, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 39, 1589.
13. R. C. VICKERY, *J. Molec. Spectrosc.*, 1956, 2, 308.
14. L. K. A. STAVELY and T. RANDALL, *Discussions Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 26, 157.

Potentiometric Studies of Metal Chelates of Tiron with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III)

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ALTHOUGH chelating properties of tiron have been reported with a number of metals¹⁻³, no attempt appears to have been made to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of its chelates with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III). In the present communication, the proton-ligand stability constants of tiron, the thermodynamic stability constants of its chelates with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III) and thermodynamic changes (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) accompanying complex formation have been reported.

Experimental

The solution of beryllium sulphate (Russian), copper sulphate (BDH, AR) and aluminium nitrate (E. Merck) were prepared in double distilled water and standardised by standard analytical methods. The solutions of tiron (Hopkins and Williams, England) and sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were also prepared in double distilled water. The pH-titrations were carried out at varying ionic strengths (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3M) and temperatures (30° and 40°) with a Phillips precision pH meter (PR 9405M) using standard glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

The Calvin Bjerrum titration technique^{4,5} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ has been used to

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